

FOREIGN EXPERIENCES CAN EMPOWER UZBEK EDUCATION AND TEACHER COMPETENCE

Nurillaev Mukhammadkhon Isroilkhon ugli

3rd grade Student of Tashkent state university of economics

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10676560>

Abstract. *Uzbekistan embarks on a transformative journey, recognizing education as its cornerstone. Traditional methods, however, restrict critical thinking and limit teacher's effectiveness. This paper explores how foreign experiences can empower Uzbek education and teacher competence. Drawing inspiration from Finland's student-centered approach and Singapore's rigorous standards, the paper proposes concrete avenues for action: teacher exchange programs, online resource platforms, and international partnerships. By investing in teachers, nurturing their competence, and embracing international collaboration, Uzbekistan can unlock its educational potential, empowering future generations to flourish in a rapidly evolving world. This journey requires navigating cultural differences, adapting best practices, and strategically allocating resources, but the potential rewards are immeasurable. Building the future, brick by brick, with teachers as architects of change – this is the promise Uzbek education holds, awaiting to be unlocked.*

Keywords: *Education, Teacher competence, foreign experiences, student-centered learning, rigorous standards, collaboration, online resources, partnerships, empowerment.*

Uzbekistan is a nation undergoing a remarkable transformation. Education, recognized as the cornerstone of this progress, stands at the forefront of this journey. Yet, challenges remain. Traditional, teacher-centered methods hold back the potential for critical thinking and creativity, while limited exposure to contemporary approaches restricts teachers' ability to cater to diverse learning styles.

But beyond its borders, a world of inspiration awaits. By harnessing the best practices gleaned from foreign experiences, Uzbekistan can unlock the true potential of its education system, empowering teachers to become the architects of a brighter future. Let's embark on a journey of discovery, exploring how these international insights can pave the way for a more enriching and empowering educational landscape.

Learning from Global Leaders: Finland, with its consistently high rankings in international assessments, offers a compelling model. Imagine classrooms buzzing with collaborative activities, where students take ownership of their learning through project-based explorations and inquiry-driven approaches. Technology seamlessly integrates into lessons, not as a distraction, but as a powerful tool for discovery and expression. This student-centered philosophy, where teachers act as facilitators rather than sole deliverers of knowledge, is a paradigm shift waiting to be embraced.

Across the globe, Singapore offers valuable lessons in academic rigor and teacher training. Imagine educators equipped with cutting-edge pedagogical skills, honed through intensive programs and ongoing professional development. Standardized tests still play a role, but they are just one piece of a comprehensive assessment system that measures critical thinking, problem-solving, and real-world skills. This commitment to high standards, coupled with ongoing support for teachers, creates fertile ground for academic excellence.

More Than Just Inspiration: Simply admiring these models from afar won't suffice. Uzbekistan needs a roadmap to translate these insights into tangible action. Consider these potential pathways:

Embracing Exchange: Imagine teachers stepping into vibrant Finnish classrooms, observing firsthand the power of student-centered learning. Conversely, experienced educators from abroad could share their expertise in Singaporean classrooms, fostering cross-cultural understanding and knowledge exchange. Such exchange programs, carefully designed and implemented, can be bridges of transformation.

Unlocking Online Resources: Imagine teachers across Uzbekistan, regardless of location, accessing a treasure trove of high-quality online resources. Imagine interactive modules on flipped classrooms, project-based learning, and technology integration, translated into Uzbek and readily available at the click of a mouse. Such online platforms can democratize access to knowledge, empowering teachers nationwide.

Building Partnerships: Imagine Uzbek universities forging strong bonds with renowned institutions abroad. Imagine joint research projects exploring effective teaching methods, collaborative curriculum development initiatives, and even virtual teacher mentoring programs. These partnerships can be catalysts for innovation, drawing on collective expertise to fuel progress.

Investing in the Architects of Change: Empowering teachers isn't just about providing resources; it's about recognizing their pivotal role in shaping the future. Imagine teachers who are not simply dispensers of knowledge, but passionate facilitators, mentors, and guides. Imagine classrooms where creativity thrives, critical thinking is celebrated, and every student feels empowered to reach their full potential. This vision can only become reality by investing in teachers, nurturing their competence, and igniting their passion for lifelong learning.

A Journey Shared is a Journey Worth Taking: The road ahead may not be without its challenges. Cultural differences need to be navigated, best practices adapted to local contexts, and resources strategically allocated. Yet, the potential rewards are immeasurable. By embarking on this journey of international collaboration, Uzbekistan can unlock its educational potential, empowering its future generations to thrive in a rapidly changing world. Remember, education is not merely about imparting knowledge; it's about building the future, brick by brick, with teachers as the architects of change. So, let's join hands, share our experiences, and together, craft an educational landscape that empowers Uzbekistan's future.

It should be noted that the development of the system of pedagogical education in Uzbekistan is being provided through research and practical implementation of modern principles of professional pedagogy, one of which is the principle of perspective-advanced training of future teachers; the comparative analysis of the trends in the current training of teaching staff in Uzbekistan and abroad shows the similarity and difference of some approaches to this problem. Most scientists dealing with the problems of teacher education in Uzbekistan note that the term "competitiveness of a specialist" is inappropriate for a teacher. As you know, competitive ability plays an important role for a specialist in the labor market. The National Doctrine of Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan pays special attention to the need to further improve the education system and improve the quality of training and the level of qualification of teaching staff.

Conclusion. As Uzbekistan strides towards progress, its education system holds the key to unlocking its true potential. Embracing the best practices gleaned from abroad – from the student-centered ethos of Finland to the rigorous standards of Singapore – can empower teachers to become the architects of a brighter future. By fostering collaboration, investing in resources, and recognizing the pivotal role of educators, Uzbekistan can build an educational landscape that fosters critical thinking, ignites creativity, and empowers every student to reach their full potential. Remember, this journey starts with a single step, a bridge built through shared experiences, leading towards a future where education truly transforms lives.

REFERENCES

1. M.V. Fominykh,. Development of the Pedagogical Educational System in Conditions of Modern Society ISSN: 2357-1330 <https://dx.doi.org/10.15405/epsbs.2019.03.34>
2. Wilfred Lau., Means to an End: A Comparative Review of Finland and Singapore’s Basic Education Systems
3. Akter, A. ., (2014). Immigrant Students' Academic Performance in Australia, New Zealand, Canada and Singapore. Joint AARE-NZARE 2014 Conference Papers. Adelaide: Flinders University.
4. Fayzievna H. M. Ways of professional training of children with the limited opportunities //Social and Natural Sciences Journal. – 2012. – T. 4.
5. Khakimova M. F., Kayumova M. S. Factors that increase the effectiveness of hybrid teaching in a digital educational environment //Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Future Networks & Distributed Systems. – 2022. – C. 370-375.
6. Xakimova M. THE NECESSITY OF INCREASING THE SOCIAL ACTIVITY OF WOMEN IN CREATING FAMILY WELL-BEING //Архив научных исследований. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 1.
7. Kayumova M. Bo‘lajak mutaxassislarni tayyorlashda ta’lim va ishlab chiqarishning o‘zaro bog‘liqligini ta’minlash //Архив научных исследований. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 1.